

IS IT A CASE OF CONTRACEPTIVE FAILURES? THE MENACE OF UNINTENDED PREGNANCIES AMONG HIV-POSITIVE WOMEN OF REPRODUCTIVE AGE.

Oguntade Racheal Tomilola¹, Ogunrombi Modupe Olufunmilayo², Abia Luther King³, Ojewole Elizabeth Bolanle¹

¹Discipline of Pharmaceutical Sciences, College of Health Sciences, University of KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa.

²Department of Clinical Pharmacology and Therapeutics, School of Medicine, Sefako Makgatho Health Sciences University, Pretoria, South Africa.

³Antimicrobial Research Unit, College of Health Sciences, University of KwaZulu-Natal, Durban, South Africa.

Correspondence: Oguntade Racheal Tomilola.

Corresponding Author's Email: 218088004@stu.ukzn.ac.za

Corresponding Author's Mobile No: +27736413434

Abstract

This study provides the baseline information on how contraceptive failures impact unintended pregnancies among Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV)-positive women in South Africa and identify possible risk factors associated with contraceptive failures. It is a retrospective analysis of the South African National HIV Prevalence, Incidence, Behavior and Communication Survey (SABSSM) dataset. Data relating to HIV-positive women and contraceptive use were analysed using STATA version 1. The analysed data showed that contraceptive failure was common among HIV-positive women, and the highest prevalence was among women aged 30-34 years. The knowledge and use of contraceptives were generally high among the population, although the use was based on self-reporting. There was no association between contraceptive failures and age, educational status, employment status, geographical location, or antiretroviral therapy initiation. It was hence concluded that prospective and real-time studies are critical to further understand the menace of contraceptive failures among HIV-positive women. This will furnish policymakers and healthcare professionals with relevant information and counselling that HIV-positive women require to make informed choices regarding contraception.

Keyword: contraceptive failures, unintended pregnancy, HIV-positive women, prevalence, contraception, South Africa.

Corresponding Author email: 218088004@stu.ukzn.ac.za

website: www.academyjsekad.edu.ng

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1.0 INTRODUCTION

Contraception is a means to prevent unintended pregnancies. The use of contraception implies that the woman or couple is not ready to have a child and, therefore, desires to avoid pregnancy. There are various reasons why a woman and/or a man, or a couple, may want to prevent pregnancies intentionally. Some of these reasons include marital status, age, recency of prior birth, financial situation, or the number of living children (Kim & Yi, 2024; Yalew et al., 2023) is an integral part of expressing reproductive health rights- the right to decide the number and spacing of children (WHO., 2020). Therefore, the use of contraception has increased over the years among the 1.9 billion women of reproductive age globally. As of 2020, 842 million people were already using contraceptives, including condoms, pills, injectables, and implants (WHO., 2020). Various studies have also revealed that women living with the Human Immunodeficiency Virus (WLWHIV) have reported they use contraceptives (Amsalu et al., 2023; Mwalye, 2022). The burden of HIV in the sub-Saharan African region cannot be overemphasized, especially in Southern Africa (UNAIDS, 2021). Women and girls are mostly affected by HIV infection, accounting for 63% of all new HIV infections in 2021, 4000 of which occurred in sub-Saharan Africa, making it a global public health challenge (UNAIDS, 2021). The phenomenon of unintended pregnancies continues to be a global health challenge and it is a common trend among women living with HIV

despite the availability and utilization of contraceptives (Omisakin & Adedini, 2024). Unintended pregnancy is unwanted or mistimed, and contraception is a proven effective way to prevent unintended pregnancies (Sarder et al., 2021). Contraception has a dual advantage of preventing unintended pregnancies among HIV-positive women and ensuring safe and healthy pregnancies among those who desire to be pregnant (Grant-Maidment et al., 2022). Contraception also plays a vital role in curbing HIV infections in newborns and is a very cost-effective strategy for preventing mother-to-child transmission (PMTCT) (Feyissa et al., 2020; Sherwood et al., 2021). The use of contraception among HIV-positive women prevents an estimated 43,559 new infant HIV infections annually across 70 countries, with South Africa having the highest aversion to infant infections (9441).

Several factors influence the incidence of unintended pregnancies among HIV-positive women. Some of these factors include age, parity, unmet need for contraception, contraceptive methods, lack of knowledge, marital status, antiretroviral therapy (ART) initiation/therapy, contraceptive misuse, and contraceptive failures (Daniel et al., 2023; Oguntade et al., 2023; Teklu et al., 2021).

Contraceptive failure is among the most significant risk factors for unintended pregnancies globally (Gelaw et al., 2023; Teklu et al., 2021). Annually, 74 million unintended

pregnancies occur in the developing world; thirty percent of these unintended pregnancies are caused by contraceptive failure among women using modern or traditional contraceptive methods. Contraceptive failure could be method- or user-related. A method-related contraceptive failure occurs if a contraceptive method fails to work as expected. In contrast, a user-related contraceptive failure arises from inconsistent or incorrect use of a contraceptive method (Kupohiyi et al., 2023; Sarder et al., 2021)

Risk factors for contraceptive failures include young age, marital status (never married), parity, wealth status, and race (Iyanda et al., 2023). Other factors that may lead to contraceptive failure include the possibility of drug-drug interactions, especially among HIV-positive women on ART, and the method of contraception (long-acting methods have lower failure rates than short-acting methods (Murray et al., 2020; Pfizer et al., 2020).

The resultant effect of contraceptive failure is unintended pregnancy, which is a significant challenge among WLWHIV, who are more prone to dangers associated with unintended pregnancies and require special attention (Ngumbau et al., 2021). A recent household antenatal survey in South Africa reported that 51.6% of the women had unintended pregnancies, and women who were aware of their HIV status had higher odds of unintended pregnancies (Woldesenbet et al., 2021). Babies

born to HIV-positive mothers have a higher likelihood of adverse outcomes like mother-to-child transmission (MCT) and mortality (Gebremedhim et al., 2025). It is, therefore, critical that the issue of contraceptive failure is well understood to help foster a better sexual and reproductive life among HIV-positive women and, in turn, improve their quality of life. This study, therefore, aimed to present baseline information on the extent of contraceptive failure among HIV-positive women and identify possible risk factors.

2.0 MATERIALS AND METHOD

Data was analysed from the 2012 South African National HIV Prevalence, Incidence, and Behavior Survey (SABSSM) (HSRC. 2018). Statistical analysis was done using summary presentation by proportions, chi-square tests, and comparison of proportions using t-tests.

This dataset comprises four individual datasets: data for guardians for children to 11 years, data for children 12 years to 14 years, data for youths and adults 15 years and older, and 'individuals' information from the visiting point dataset. The information contained in the dataset includes sexual debut, condoms, alcohol and substance use, health and violence in the community, biographical data, media, communication and norms, knowledge and perception of HIV/AIDS, male circumcision, partners and partner characteristics, vulnerability, HIV testing, general perceptions about government, health, and violence in the community.

Information on contraceptive use and awareness was also available in this dataset. A total of 44029 cases and 917 variables are contained in the dataset. This dataset is the fourth national-level repeat survey since 2002, when the first survey was done. Data was collected across all the nine South African provinces, making it a good representation to gather baseline information on issues relating to HIV-positive women nationally.

The cohort from this study was generated from the young and adult 15 years and older dataset. Women of reproductive age (15-49 years) who were HIV-positive constituted the cohort for this study. The theoretical framework for this study is presented in the summary Table 1 and Figure 1.

Summary tables of results were generated using the STATA software package (<https://www.stata.com/>). Approval to conduct the study was obtained from the Biomedical Research Ethics Committee (BREC) of the University of KwaZulu-Natal- Reference number (BREC/00003621/2021). Authorization to use the dataset was obtained from the Human Science and Research Council (HSRC). Consent to participate is not applicable.

3.0 RESULTS

A total of 173 HIV-positive women of reproductive age (15-49) had unintended pregnancies while using contraceptives, and KwaZulu-Natal had the highest number of 32

(18.5%), followed by Limpopo with 29 (16.76%), then Northwest with 27 (15.61%). Gauteng, Eastern Cape, and Mpumalanga provinces had 19 (10.98%) each. Free State had 10 (5.78%), while Western Cape and Northern Cape each had 9 (5.2%) HIV-positive women (Table 2). The most prevalent age group was 30-34 years, with 54 women, followed by the 25-29 age group, with 45 women; the age group 15-19 years had the least prevalence of 2 respondents. Age groups 20-24 years, 35-39 years, 40-44 years, and 45-49 years had 27, 31, 11, and 3 respondents, respectively (Table 3). All the women were South African citizens of different races, mostly African (91.9%), Indian/Asian (0.58%), and the colored women were 7.51% (Table 4).

From the result obtained, about seven percent of the women were married and living with their husbands. Most women (39.3%) had a status of 'going steady,' meaning they were in a relationship but not married. Furthermore, 27.17% lived with their boyfriend but were unmarried (Table 5). Over half of the population was unemployed and looking for work (60.15%). Only about eight percent were fully employed, and 9.8% had part-time employment (Table 6). Over half of the population (50.87%) were educated up to grade 11 (Table 7). There was almost uniformity between rural and urban distribution; the urban setting had 49%, while the rural setting had 51% (Figure 2).

Knowledge about contraceptives and its use was

high among the population, with injectables taking the lead (Figures 4 and 5). Most of the women (167 out of 173) were vast in the knowledge of injectables. Likewise, the use of injectables was mostly prevalent among the population, followed by the use of contraceptive pills; 118/173 have ever used injectables, and 44/173 have ever used pills.

It is also noteworthy that most of the women (83%) were knowledgeable about the drug treatments HIV-positive pregnant women needed to reduce the risk of mother-to-child transmission of HIV (Figure 6). Sixty-nine percent of the population was already on antiretrovirals (ARVs) (Figure 7).

Regarding pregnancy, 58.38% of the women never wanted to become pregnant when they got pregnant (Figure 3). Only 21.39% wanted to be pregnant then, and 20.3% would have loved to be pregnant later. All the women (173/173) indicated that they were using contraceptives when they fell pregnant, which might be indicative of contraceptive failures (Table 4).

There was no association between contraceptive failures and geographical location, educational status, employment status, age, or ARV use. Fischer's exact values were 0.359, 0.122, 0.204, 0.348, and 0.741, respectively (Table 8).

4.0 DISCUSSION

Findings from this study have resonated with several studies that have reported that HIV-

positive women indicated contraceptive use before their pregnancy incidences (Atukunda et al., 2021; Thindwa et al., 2019; Woldesenbet et al., 20212). Even though some studies have revealed misuse or poor uptake of contraceptives, it is uncertain in this study because the participants reported a generally good uptake of contraceptives (Teklu et al., 2021) in the population. However, there is a decline/inconsistency in the type(method) of contraceptive used, as shown in Figure 4. These women may have switched contraceptive options or have discontinued at some point due to various reasons. A study done in Ghana revealed that one of the reasons for the discontinuation of contraceptives is the side effects experienced by its users (Ekholuentale et al., 2021; Ontiri et al., 2021). (Samak et al., 2021) also highlighted the need for male partner involvement to lessen the practice of contraceptive discontinuation. Furthermore, intimate partner violence(IPV) influences contraceptive use discontinuation, as reported from a study done in Nigeria to investigate the relationship between IPV and contraceptive discontinuation among sexually active married women who were at risk of getting pregnant (Kabir & Kordowicz, 2021; Kupoluyi et al., 2023).

In any case, injectables still had the highest usage rate (Figure 5), a finding in sync with findings from other studies that injectables are one of the most commonly used modern contraceptive methods among women of

various groups (Lake et al., 2024; Napyo et al., 2020; Shagaro et al., 2022; Wolesenbet et al., 2021). Most women might have preferred to use injectables because of their convenient dosing schedules and the ease of discontinuation if fertility desires change.

In this study, 173 HIV-positive women experienced contraceptive failure at some point because they had said yes to the question, "Were you using a contraceptive method when you fell pregnant? However, out of the 173 HIV-positive women, 72 (41.6%) had said they wished to be pregnant either then or later, while 101(58.4%) indicated they never wished to be pregnant. Therefore, the group that wished to be pregnant could have discontinued the contraceptive at some point. However, there was no evidence of discontinuation since no question was asked in light of this, and data on contraceptive use were solely based on participant self-reporting.

In contrast to findings from other studies by (Bradley et al., 2019; Leticee et al., 2012; Patel et al., 2017), this study found no association between age, ARV initiation, educational status, employment status, and contraceptive failures. Although these contrasting studies also focused on HIV-positive women, the sample size is not comparable to that of this study. The sample size for this study is relatively small. It may, therefore, be essential to conduct further studies that would involve direct interaction with HIV-positive women to gain an in-depth understanding of contraceptive use and failures.

Also, contraceptive use was based on self-reporting by the respondents, and one is uncertain of the reliability and validity of such information. Furthermore, there could be recall bias since most pregnancy experiences were in the past.

5.0 CONCLUSION

This study has provided baseline information on the possible occurrences of contraceptive failures among HIV-positive women, suggesting an urgent need to investigate this issue further. It is essential to know the risk factors of contraceptive failures among HIV-positive women. Prospective, qualitative, and real-time studies might be helpful in achieving a better understanding of this common phenomenon of contraceptive failure.

ABBREVIATIONS

HIV (Human Immunodeficiency Virus), SABSSM (South African National HIV prevalence, Incidence and Behavior Survey), WLWHIV (Women Living with HIV), PMTCT (prevention of mother-to-child transmission), ART (Antiretroviral therapy), WLWHIV (Women living with HIV), MCT (mother-to-child transmission), SA (South Africa), BREC (Biomedical Research Ethics Committee), HSRC (Human Science and Research Council), ARVs (antiretrovirals).

ETHICS APPROVAL AND CONSENT TO PARTICIPATE

Permission to use the dataset was obtained from

Human Science and Research Council (HSRC). Also, this study was approved by the ethics committee of UKZN (BREC) with reference number BREC/00003126/2021.

Consent to participate was not applicable because no human participation was involved.

Author contributions

RO, EO, and MO conceptualized the work. RO wrote the manuscript draft. EO, MO, and ALK supervised the draft's write-up and final editing. All authors approved the submission of the final edition of the manuscript.

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Disclosure

All authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest in this work.

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Tables and Figures

Table 1: Summary Table of Key Framework Elements

Level	Constructs & Variables
Individual	Sexual debut, condom use, HIV Knowledge, substance use, contraceptive use, health
Interpersonal	Partner characteristics, family communication, vulnerability, violence experience
Community/ society	Media, norms, violence in the community, perceptions of government, access to health services

Table 2: Distribution of HIV-POSITIVE women(respondents) by province

Province	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Western Cape	9	5.20
Eastern Cape	19	10.98
Northern Cape	9	5.20
Free State	10	5.78
KwaZulu Natal	32	18.50
Northwest	27	15.61
Gauteng	19	10.98
Mpumalanga	19	10.98
Limpopo	29	16.76
Total	173	100

Table 3: Age distribution of respondents

Age (in years)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
15-19	2	1.16
20-24	27	15.6
25-29	45	26.01
30-34	54	31.21
35-39	31	17.92
40-44	11	6.36
45-49	3	1.76
Total	173	100

Table 4: Distribution of participants (HIV positive women) by race, nationality and contraceptive use prior to conception

Variables	N	%
Race:		
African	159	91.9
Coloured	13	7.5
Asian/Indian	1	0.6
Nationality:		
South African citizens	173	100
Contraceptive use prior to conception		
Yes	173	100

Table 5: Marital status of HIV positive women who were respondents

Marital status	Frequency	Percent (%)
Married (living with husband)	12	6.94
Married (not living with husband)	6	3.47
Living together, (not married, living with boyfriend/partner)	47	27.17
Going steady(in a relationship but not married)	68	39.31
Single (not in a relationship)	32	18.50
Divorced/separated	4	2.31
Widow	3	1.73
No response	1	0.58
Total	173	100

Table 6: Employment status of HIV positive women who were respondents

Employment status	Frequency	Percent (%)
Housewife,homemaker, not looking for work	5	2.89
Housewife, homemaker, looking for work	14	8.09
Unemployed,looking for work	91	52.6
Unemployed, not looking for work	16	9.25
Sick/disabled	1	0.58
Student/pupil/learner	3	1.73
Self-employed-full time (40 hours or more per week)	1	0.58
Self-employed-part time (less than 40 hours per week)	6	3.47
Employed part time (if none of the above) less than 40 hours per week	17	9.83
Employed full time 40 hours or more per week	13	7.51
Other	6	3.47
Total	173	100

Table 7: Educational status of HIV positive women who were respondents

Educational status	Frequency	Percent
Grade 0-7	23	13.29
Grade 8-11	88	50.87
Grade 12/Post school	38	21.97
Not applicable	24	13.87
Total	173	100

Table 8: Association between characters of HIV positive women and contraceptive failures

	Desired to be pregnant	Did not desire to be pregnant	Total	Fischers exact value
<u>Geographical location</u>				
Urban-Formal/Informal	38	46	84	
Rural-Formal/Informal	34	55	89	0.359
Total	72	101	173	
<u>Educational status</u>				
Grades 0 to 7	11	12	23	
Grade 8 to 11	32	56	88	
Grade 12/Post School	21	17	38	0.122
Total	64	85	149	
<u>Employment status</u>				
Employed- Formal/Informal	13	27	40	
Unemployed	56	71	127	0.204
Total	69	98	169	
<u>Age</u>				
Below 25	15	14	29	
25 to under 30	20	25	45	
30 to under 35	24	30	54	
35 to under 40	9	22	31	0.348
Above 40	4	10	14	
	72	101	173	

Participants exposed to antiretroviral therapy

Not on ARV	51	69	120	
On ARV	21	32	53	0.741
Total	72	101	173	

Figure 1: Theoretical framework of the study

Figure 2: Geographical distribution of the HIV positive women.

Figure 3: Pregnancy intention/desire of HIV positive women

Figure 4: Knowledge of contraceptives among of HIV positive women who were respondents

Figure 5: Contraceptive use of HIV positive women who were respondents

Figure 6: Awareness of prevention of mother-to-child transmission (PMTCT).

Figure 7: Antiretroviral therapy initiation among HIV positive women who were respondents